

Controlled vocabularies in the organization and management of cultural heritage: practical guidelines

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associação portuguesa de
bibliotecários, arquivistas e documentalistas

grupo de trabalho
sistemas de informação em museus

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Who we are

associação portuguesa de
bibliotecários, arquivistas e documentalistas

**Portuguese Association of Librarians, Archivists and
Documentalists (BAD)**

**grupo de trabalho
sistemas de informação em museus**

Working Group Information Systems in Museums

Who we are

Natália Jorge

Career: Employee at Sistemas do Futuro, Lda. since 2001, working at the Department of Research and Documentation, PHD student in Museum Studies at University of Porto, researcher at The Transdisciplinary Research Centre Culture, Space and Memory (CITCEM) and member of the *Working Group Information Systems in Museums*.

Main interest: Study of controlled vocabularies in documentation and cataloging processes.

natalia@sistemasfuturo.pt

Juliana Alves

Currently a PhD student in Museum Studies at University of Porto (since 2014), researching management evaluation for procedures and practices in Museums.

Researcher at The Transdisciplinary Research Centre Culture, Space and Memory (CITCEM) and member of the *Working Group Information Systems in Museums*. Consultant in Reengineering of Document Management Processes and Consultant in Museology.

julira@yahoo.com

Who we are

Filipa Medeiros

Phd in Information Science (University of Évora in collaboration with the Carlos III University of Madrid, 2014); Integrated researcher at the Interdisciplinary Center for History, Cultures and Societies of the University of Évora (2010-). Member of the Working Group “Information Systems in Museums” (GT-SIM / BAD, 2012-); Director of the Gulbenkian Library Paris (2016-). Areas of professional and scientific activity: technical coordination and management of specialized information units; organization and representation of information; information systems in museums.

fmcm@uevora.pt

Susana Medina

She is an art historian and museologist. Doctoral student at FLUP and lecturer on Project Management for Museums at the MA of Museum Studies in the same faculty.

She holds a Master’s degree in Museum Studies (FLUP, 2008) and PG in European Cultural Planning (De Montfort University, 2005). She publishes and lectures on a regular basis. She is also a researcher at CITCEM. As a practicing museologist, she is a curator at FEUPmuseu since 2003, and integrates the task force of U.Porto Digital Museum’s project.

smedina@fe.up.pt

Agenda

- Group goal
- Methodology: what was done
- Deliverables
- Prospects for the future

Group goal

Purpose: To provide guidelines for use of controlled vocabularies.

Approach: Organization of seminars, publication of articles, dissemination of projects related to documentary languages and creation of tools in Portuguese.

Methodology: what was done

Seminar "Museum organization of knowledge systems", Lisbon, 2015.

Methodology: what was done

The screenshot displays the Zotero web interface. At the top, the Zotero logo is on the left, and user information (Welcome, julira) and navigation links (Settings, Inbox, Download, Log Out) are on the right. A search bar is located below the navigation links. The main navigation menu includes Home, My Library, Groups, People, Documentation, Forums, and Get Involved. The breadcrumb trail indicates the current location: Home > Groups > gt-sim > Library > Vocabulários controlados. The left sidebar shows a tree view of the library structure, with 'Vocabulários controlados' highlighted. The main content area displays a table of controlled vocabularies with columns for Title, Creator, and Date Modified. The table is highlighted with a green border.

	Title	Creator	Date Modified
<input type="checkbox"/>	1220.0 - ASCO - Australian Standard Classification of Occupa...	Australian Bureau of Statistics	9/12/2016 7:06 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	1272.0 - Australian Standard Classification of Education (AS...	Australian Bureau of Statistics	9/12/2016 7:03 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	AFS Ethnographic Thesaurus	American Folklore Society	9/8/2016 7:02 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	AGRICOLA - Subject category Codes	OVID and National Agricultural Library (NAL)	9/8/2016 7:05 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	AGRIFOREST Thesaurus	Viikki Campus Library, Helsinki University	7/24/2015 2:44 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	AGROVOC Multilingual agriculture thesaurus	People page	9/8/2016 9:16 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	AMICO Art Museum Image Consortium	Art Museum Network	9/12/2016 4:16 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	APAIS thesaurus	Australian Public Affairs Information Service	9/12/2016 4:24 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	APT Australian Pictorial Thesaurus	State Library of New South Wales	9/12/2016 4:47 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	ASFA Thesaurus	FAO	6/13/2015 4:52 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	ATBD - Ambito Culturale	Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione	6/10/2015 11:39 PM
<input type="checkbox"/>	ATHENA Mineral Database	ATHENA and Perroud	9/12/2016 7:00 PM

Almeida, M. J. de, Ferreira, F., Medeiros, F., Patrão, S., & Salgado, A. (n.d.). Centro de documentação virtual | Zotero | Groups GT_SIM. Retrieved April 28, 2017, from <https://www.zotero.org/groups/81851/gt-sim>

Methodology: what was done

Deliverables

Subgroup Terminologies of the Working Group Information Systems in Museums of the Portuguese Association of Librarians, Archivists and Documentalists (BAD).

Deliverables

*Figura 2: Jarras provenientes da Igreja de Santo Ildefonso, Porto.
Coleção de cerâmica do Museu Nacional Soares dos Reis.*

Deliverables

1. Project presentation;
2. Reference to the prerequisites for the development of documentation projects (data structure, registration procedures, data syntax and terminology);
3. Presentation of national and international standards for the development of controlled vocabularies;
4. Methodological and conceptual framework;
5. Typologies of controlled vocabularies;
6. Tools related to controlled vocabularies;
7. National and international reference projects;
8. Guidelines for the creation of controlled vocabularies;
9. Future development perspectives.

Prospects for the future

- Debate among professionals: review and improvements
- Glossary
- Toolkits
- Trainings

Prospects for the future

Thank you!
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Obrigada

Juliana Alves, julira@yahoo.com

Natália Jorge, natalia@sistemasfuturo.pt

Filipa Medeiros, fmcm@uevora.pt

Susana Medina, smedina@fe.up.pt